

Neural-Network solver of ideal MHD equilibria

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Abstract

We present a novel approach to compute three-dimensional Magnetohydrodynamic equilibria with isotropic pressure profiles and nested surfaces by parametrizing Fourier modes with artificial neural networks. The full nonlinear global force residual of single equilibria across the volume in real space is then minimized with first order optimizers and compared to equilibria computed by conventional solvers. Already, we observe competitive computational cost to arrive at the same minimum residuals computable with existing codes. With increased computational cost, lower minima of the residual are computed with the neural networks, establishing a new lower bound for the force residual. We use minimally complex neural networks, and we expect significant improvements for solving not only single equilibria with neural networks, but also for creating neural network models valid over continuous distributions of equilibria.

1 Introduction

Magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) models describe experimental and astrophysical plasmas as single species fluids with electromagnetic effects in the long-wavelength and low-frequency limit. By considering the fluid as a perfect conductor without electric resistance, this system of Partial Differential Equations (PDEs) reduces to the *ideal* MHD equations. The equilibrium states of ideal MHD are a baseline in the description of magnetically confined, ring-shaped plasmas in fusion experiments. One goal of such experiments is the achievement of self-sustaining hot plasmas in a torus that are amenable to the release of excess energy by fusing light nuclei.

Computation of an equilibrium magnetic field is a first step for many subsequent calculations in axisymmetric and non-axisymmetric plasmas. Assuming the magnetic field to be axisymmetric reduces the ideal MHD equations to the Grad-Shafranov equation, but this assumption can be too strong for control applications of axisymmetric tokamaks [1, 2]. Analytical models for the 3D ideal MHD equations exist for high-pressure and large-aspect configurations [3], low-order Fourier modes of the magnetic field in a subset of reactor-relevant stellarators [4] and for the description of equilibrium magnetic fields close to axis [5]. Still, global analytic solutions of ideal MHD equilibria with finite pressure in tori are missing [6], which motivated the creation of many numerical solvers for 3D plasma equilibria [7–12]. The optimization space of non-axisymmetric fields is orders of magnitude larger than that of axisymmetric devices [13], and certain geometries only become computable with novel solvers, for example, figure-8 stellarators [14]. An assumption that many solvers implement, especially in optimization workflows, is the existence of nested magnetic *flux surfaces*. With this

assumption, magnetic islands and chaotic regions are excluded in the description of the plasma, and this simplifies computation by ensuring integrability over the whole plasma volume. Flux surfaces are isobaric surfaces on which the toroidal magnetic flux $2\pi\psi$ and poloidal magnetic flux $2\pi\chi$ are constant [13]. The existence of flux surfaces in three-dimensional plasma boundaries is proven for stepped pressure profiles including island regions close to axisymmetry [15], but not for strongly non-axisymmetric cases with continuous pressure profiles.

Fast and accurate computational models for 3D ideal MHD equilibria can enable real-time control of plasmas, flight-simulators and other data-intensive applications. To evaluate artificial neural networks (NNs) as a parametrization for Fourier-decomposed, 3D ideal MHD equilibria, we examine the lower bound on NN complexity. Specifically, we investigate the performance of two-hidden-layer multilayer perceptrons (MLPs) and their hidden layer widths to represent Fourier modes of magnetic fields of single fixed-boundary equilibria with isotropic pressure profiles.

1.1 Motivation

Fast, accurate and continuous models of three-dimensional plasma equilibrium evolution expedite data analysis pipelines [16], enhance real-time control [1] and enable a zoo of other data-intensive applications for stellarators and tokamaks. Stellarators with inherently stable plasmas rely much less on active control than tokamaks, but control of transport or turbulence in stellarators will likely benefit from rapid ideal MHD equilibrium information. Significantly reducing the runtime for individual equilibrium solves is of great interest to real-time interpretation of diagnostic data [17]. This work explores the minimum size of MLP required for solving single equilibria. The results of the presented investigation (see figure 6b and 6a) are a valuable starting-point to construct continuous operator models that support rapid inference. Currently existing stellarator equilibrium solvers are not able to provide equilibria in less than $\mathcal{O}(10^{-3}\text{s})$ without massive parallelization, driving up operational costs for real-time control systems. Creating a look-up table of equilibria for the configuration space of a specific device using a conventional solver will incur some interpolation error. NNs provide continuous output functions and, trained on PDEs or diagnostic data, can achieve super-resolution and reveal hidden relations between diagnostics [18, 19].

MERLO et al. [16] shows benefit to stellarator optimization and acceleration of bayesian inference by several orders of magnitude using an operator model trained on the configuration space of Wendelstein 7-X (W7-X) as calculated by the ideal MHD solver VMEC.

This work tries to answer if it is possible to skip conventional solvers altogether, not creating any datasets and thus relying only on the physics of the equilibrium problem to train NN. Training a single NN model on a single equilibrium is a first step in that direction. We extrapolate from the results of VAN MILLIGEN, JIMÉNEZ and TRIBALDOS [20], where a MLP with one hidden layer was sufficient to solve stellarator equilibria, and investigate minimally complex MLP with two hidden layers trained solely on the ideal MHD force residual. Furthermore, PALUZO-HIDALGO, GONZALEZ-DIAZ and GUTIÉRREZ-NARANJO [21] prove that maps between triangulable spaces, which the authors write include most real-world problems, can be solved with two-hidden-layer NNs.

Like the modern ideal MHD solver DESC, the code implementing this work utilizes the automatic differentiation library JAX, which offers computation along a graph with tangent spaces, enabling the calculation of first order derivatives with a small computational and memory overhead [22]. Higher order derivative computation incurs exponentially larger resource requirements and the presented approach requires computation of second order derivatives because we optimize for the strong form of the ideal MHD residual. This automatic differentiation saves compute time and provides more precise gradients compared to finite differencing gradient computation schemes in larger stellarator optimization workflows [23].

NNs applied to solve physics equations in nuclear fusion research is promising [24], and this work introduces a bridge connecting NNs with the ideal MHD equilibrium problem. The modular approach of this work allows for simple investigation of novel NN architectures, training schemes and optimizers, and also the addition of new physics.

1.2 3D ideal MHD equilibrium

Ideal MHD equilibria are computed by minimizing either the weak or strong form of the ideal, stationary MHD equations in a map between two different coordinate systems. One of these coordinate systems is chosen such that the magnetic field lines are straight, namely the magnetic coordinates, and the other is the cartesian or cylindrical coordinate system. This work uses the inverse formulation, that is the MLPs map from magnetic back to cylindrical coordinates $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = [s, \theta, \zeta]^T \rightarrow [R, \lambda, Z]^T$, to minimize residuals of finite-pressure, fixed-boundary ideal MHD equilibria evaluated in the cartesian frame.

Stellarator equilibria are often computed with toroidal symmetry with N_{FP} equal toroidal segments, each segment, or field period, occupying $2\pi/N_{\text{FP}}$ of the full torus. In the magnetic coordinates, the normalized flux

$s = \psi/\psi_b \in [0, 1]$ can act as the radial coordinate with ψ_b denoting the toroidal flux enclosed by the plasma boundary, $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$ is a poloidal angle in geometric coordinates and $\zeta = \phi \in [0, 2\pi/N_{\text{FP}}]$ is a toroidal angle equal to the geometric cylindrical angle. R and Z are part of the cylindrical coordinate system with its origin coinciding with the major axis of the plasma. In the inverse approach to the ideal MHD equilibrium problem, the magnetic field is parametrized by some continuous radial coordinate, which imposes a continuous distribution of flux surfaces, yielding a nested set of flux surfaces. It follows that no magnetic islands or chaotic regions can be expressed in the inverse approach, however, this assumption simplifies the computation compared to the direct map $[R, \lambda, Z]^T \rightarrow [s, \theta, \zeta]^T$.

It is common practice to decompose the poloidal and toroidal angles in a 2D Fourier series with angle $\varphi_{\text{F},mn} = m\theta - nN_{\text{FP}}\zeta$. Fourier expanding the independent variables reduces the input dimensionality of the ideal MHD equilibrium problem by two: $s \rightarrow (R, \lambda, Z)$ [25], but comes with the cost associated with finite truncation of the chosen basis. The subscript m denotes poloidal modes as $m = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, M-1\}$ for a total number of poloidal modes M and the subscript n denotes toroidal modes $n = \{-N, -N+1, \dots, 0, \dots, N-1, N\}$ for a total number of toroidal modes of $2N+1$. The dependent variables are then split into cosine and sine components, denoted by superscripts c and s respectively (see equations (40)-(42)). Coordinates $X \in \{R, \lambda, Z\}$ can then be recovered via the series

$$X = \sum_{mn} X_{mn}^c \cos(\varphi_{\text{F},mn}) + X_{mn}^s \sin(\varphi_{\text{F},mn}). \quad (1)$$

The renormalizing stream function λ and the Z coordinate are periodic functions with zero mean, i.e. $\int \int X d\theta d\zeta = 0$ for $X \in \{\lambda, Z\}$, which is analogous to setting the $(m, n) = (0, 0)$ mode to 0. λ converts the geometric poloidal angle θ to the magnetic poloidal angle θ^* : $\theta^* = \theta + \lambda$ in which field lines are straight and also facilitates numerical convergence by condensing shape information of the flux surfaces into the lower modes of the Fourier series expansion [7].

The exact definition of the poloidal angle θ can be set freely as long as it is periodic, and the Jacobian of the transformation between the two coordinate systems stays finite and does not change sign. Lastly, stellarator equilibria are often assumed to be up-down symmetric in at least two toroidal angles per field period, expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} R(s, \theta, \zeta) &= R(s, -\theta, -\zeta) \\ Z(s, \theta, \zeta) &= -Z(s, -\theta, -\zeta) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

If this *stellarator symmetry* [26] is assumed, the computational grid can be reduced by half in the poloidal coordinate $\theta \in [0, \pi]$ and the non-symmetric Fourier

modes are omitted, which further reduces computational cost: $R_{mn}^s = Z_{mn}^c = \lambda_{mn}^c = 0$. Ideal MHD equilibria with nested flux surfaces, isotropic pressure and a fixed plasma boundary are then defined on the map between the magnetic and geometric coordinates and fully characterized by three invariants: The radial pressure profile $p(s)$, the rotational transform profile $\iota(s)$ and the boundary geometry, in the following enforced in Fourier space as $R_{mn}^c(s=1)$ and $Z_{mn}^s(s=1)$ [27]. Replacement of the rotational transform profile with the toroidal current profile is also possible but not used in this work. In the remainder of this section, the computation of the force residual is detailed:

The covariant basis vectors of the inverse map are

$$\mathbf{e}_s = \begin{bmatrix} \partial_s R \\ 0 \\ \partial_s Z \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{e}_\theta = \begin{bmatrix} \partial_\theta R \\ 0 \\ \partial_\theta Z \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{e}_\zeta = \begin{bmatrix} \partial_\zeta R \\ R \\ \partial_\zeta Z \end{bmatrix}$$

and their contravariants are $\mathbf{e}^i = \nabla_i = \frac{\mathbf{e}_j \times \mathbf{e}_k}{\sqrt{g}}$ with (i, j, k) a cyclic permutation of $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$. The partial derivative is denoted with $\partial_{\alpha_i} X = \frac{\partial X}{\partial \alpha_i}$ for $X \in \{R, \lambda, Z\}$.

$$\sqrt{g} = \mathbf{e}_s \cdot \mathbf{e}_\theta \times \mathbf{e}_\zeta = (\mathbf{e}^s \cdot \mathbf{e}^\theta \times \mathbf{e}^\zeta)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

is the Jacobian of the map. Then, the metric tensor components can be easily computed [7]:

$$g_{ij} = \mathbf{e}_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_j = \partial_i R \partial_j R + R^2 \partial_i \phi \partial_j \phi + \partial_i Z \partial_j Z \quad (4)$$

$$g^{ij} = \mathbf{e}^i \cdot \mathbf{e}^j \quad (5)$$

The force residual is the remainder of the ideal MHD equations, which models the pressure balance between confining magnetic field and pressure exerted by the plasma. In steady-state ($\partial_t = 0$), the magnetic field has to counteract the plasma pressure for which the ideal MHD equations reduce to

$$\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B} = \nabla p \quad (6)$$

$$\mu_0 \mathbf{J} = \nabla \times \mathbf{B} \quad (7)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad (8)$$

with the vacuum permeability μ_0 . In the absence of magnetic islands, chaotic regions and plasma resistivity, the flux surfaces may be viewed as a continuous distribution of isobaric surfaces for $s \in [0, 1]$, and the contravariant magnetic field can be expressed as [13]

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{B} &= \nabla \zeta \times \nabla \chi + \nabla \psi \times \nabla \theta^* \\ &= B^s \mathbf{e}_s + B^\theta \mathbf{e}_\theta + B^\zeta \mathbf{e}_\zeta \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The assumption of nested flux surfaces for the magnetic topology is $B^s = \mathbf{B} \cdot \nabla s = 0$. The magnetic field (9)

together with Gauss's law (8) results in the remaining magnetic field components

$$\mathbf{B} = \frac{\partial_s \psi}{\sqrt{g}} (\iota(s) - \partial_\zeta \lambda) \mathbf{e}_\theta + (1 + \partial_\theta \lambda) \mathbf{e}_\zeta \quad (10)$$

The magnetic field's covariant components are computed via

$$B_i = B^\theta g_{i\theta} + B^\zeta g_{i\zeta}. \quad (11)$$

Using Ampere's law (7), the contravariant current components are expressed as

$$J^i = \frac{1}{\mu_0 \sqrt{g}} (\partial_j B_k - \partial_k B_j) \quad (12)$$

for cyclic permutations (i, j, k) of $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$. The \mathbf{B} -field (10) inserted into the force balance equation (6) reveals the two independent parts of the force residual [7]:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F} &= F_s \mathbf{e}^s + F_h \mathbf{e}^h \\ &= (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B} - \mu_0 \nabla p \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

with $\mathbf{e}^h = \sqrt{g}(B^\zeta \mathbf{e}^\theta - B^\theta \mathbf{e}^\zeta) = \nabla \theta - \iota \nabla \zeta$ denoting the helical direction. Using the magnitude of this force vector

$$\|\mathbf{F}\|_2 = \sqrt{F_s^2 \|\mathbf{e}^s\|_2 + F_h^2 \|\mathbf{e}^h\|_2} \quad (14)$$

allows for a fair comparison between equilibrium solutions of different numerical solvers on equal computational grids. This metric is then normalized with the gradient of the magnetic pressure $\langle |\nabla |B|^2 / (2\mu_0) \rangle_{\text{vol}}$ with $\nabla |B|^2$ given by

$$\nabla |B|^2 = 2(|B| \nabla |B|) \quad (15)$$

and $|B| = \sqrt{\mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}}$. Another characteristic of the magnetic topology is the straight field line angle θ^* , which is also used in comparisons between solvers. The volume average of some quantity (\cdot) is denoted by $\langle (\cdot) \rangle_{\text{vol}}$ and defined as

$$\langle (\cdot) \rangle_{\text{vol}} = \frac{1}{V} \int (\cdot) \sqrt{g} d\boldsymbol{\alpha} \quad (16)$$

with the plasma volume $V = \int \sqrt{g} d\boldsymbol{\alpha}$.

Despite all the assumptions in this model, it is challenging to solve, partly due to the mixed elliptic-hyperbolic form of the equations and finite truncation of basis functions [28].

Many different solvers have been created, each with a unique parametrization and associated costs. In the following, we will describe the numerical solvers **VMEC** and **DESC**, focusing on the important aspects of each solver, introduce the NN-based approach in more detail and finish with a comparison.

2 Related Work

2.1 VMEC

VMEC [7] is the workhorse of stellarator optimization [29, 30], equilibrium reconstruction [30–33] and inference of plasma parameters [30, 34, 35]. Several experimental devices were constructed using **VMEC** in its free-boundary mode [36, 37]. Instead of the force residual (14), **VMEC** uses the weak formulation and minimizes the potential energy W_{pot} with a variational principle in magnetic coordinates

$$W_{\text{pot}} = \int \frac{|B|^2}{2\mu_0} |\sqrt{g}| d\boldsymbol{\alpha} + \int_0^1 \frac{M_m(\rho)}{\gamma - 1} (V')^{1-\gamma} d\rho \quad (17)$$

with the specific heat ratio (or adiabatic index) γ and some constant mass function $M_m(\rho)$. $V'(s)$ is the radial derivative of the volume $V(s)$ enclosed by the flux surface at s

$$V(s) = \int_0^s \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \sqrt{g} ds d\theta d\zeta. \quad (18)$$

Variationally minimizing the potential energy reduces the computational load of minimization because first order gradients need to be calculated in the weak formulation only [7]. Given stellarator symmetric equilibria, the dependent variables R , λ and Z are expanded in Fourier series

$$R(s, \theta, \zeta) = \sum_{mn} R_{mn}^c \cos(\varphi_{F,mn}) \quad (19)$$

$$\lambda(s, \theta, \zeta) = \sum_{mn} \lambda_{mn}^s \sin(\varphi_{F,mn}) \quad (20)$$

$$Z(s, \theta, \zeta) = \sum_{mn} Z_{mn}^s \sin(\varphi_{F,mn}). \quad (21)$$

Internally, **VMEC** uses a specialized double Fourier representation that is both efficient in terms of information in low modes and a unique representation. This new representation fulfills the minimization of the following power spectrum

$$M_{\text{sp}} = \sum_{mn} m^2 (R_{mn}^2 + Z_{mn}^2) \quad (22)$$

by construction [38]. To further increase solution efficiency, **VMEC** uses pre-conditioning of its radial discretization [39] and calculates values on a *half-grid*, which only includes points $\theta \in [0, \pi]$ if the equilibrium possesses stellarator symmetry. Last but not least, a common pattern in **VMEC** is the refinement of the radial grid, starting with a coarse discretization of the flux surfaces and reaching the final solution on a fine discretization—but this can lead to unphysical current spikes in the final solution at the coarse gridpoints [40]. **VMEC** is a finite difference solver with associated drawbacks, for

example, the requirement to interpolate values between flux surfaces and the introduction of numerical error due to finite discretization, and the magnetic axis calculated by VMEC lacks precision [40]. Despite its minor drawbacks, VMEC is a viable candidate as a ground truth because of its empirical validation and widespread use in fusion research. These drawbacks and the inability of current solvers to compute continuous models valid over continuous distributions of equilibria also motivated the presented work to inspect NNs parametrizing VMEC's Fourier basis (see equations (19)- (21)) for single equilibria as a first step.

2.2 DESC stellarator equilibrium solver

The pseudo-spectral solver DESC uses a global, orthogonal basis set (on the unit disc) consisting of Zernike polynomials of the radial coordinate $\rho = \sqrt{s}$ and angle θ in conjunction with Fourier expanding ζ . This basis avoids VMEC's issues at the magnetic axis, reduces the number of parameters and is free from interpolation error between flux surfaces [8]. Replacing the finite differencing scheme of VMEC in radial direction with Zernike polynomials of order L_{ZP} provides a spectral parametrization in all three independent coordinates (ρ, θ, ζ) . For each $X \in \{R, \lambda, Z\}$ the Fourier Zernike basis is

$$X(\rho, \theta, \zeta) = \sum_{m=-M_D}^{M_D} \sum_{n=-N}^N \sum_{l=0}^{L_{ZP}} X_{lmn} \mathcal{L}_l^m(\rho, \theta) \mathcal{F}^n(\zeta) \quad (23)$$

where M_D is different from VMEC's M because it is the maximum poloidal mode number instead of the total number of modes [40]. The Zernike polynomial defined on $\rho \in [0, 1]$ and $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$ is

$$\mathcal{L}_l^m(\rho, \theta) = \begin{cases} \mathcal{R}_l^{|m|} \cos(|m|\theta) & \text{if } m \geq 0 \\ \mathcal{R}_l^{|m|} \sin(|m|\theta) & \text{if } m < 0 \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

with the Fourier decomposition defined for $\zeta \in [0, 2\pi]$ as

$$\mathcal{F}^n(\zeta) = \begin{cases} \cos(|n|N_{FP} \zeta) & \text{if } n \geq 0 \\ \sin(|n|N_{FP} \zeta) & \text{if } n < 0 \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

The shifted Jacobi polynomial $\mathcal{R}_l^{|m|}$, defined for $m \geq 0$, is

$$\mathcal{R}_l^{|m|}(\rho) = \sum_{s=0}^{(l-|m|)/2} \frac{(-1)^s (l-s)!}{s! \left(\frac{l+|m|}{2} - s\right)! \left(\frac{l-|m|}{2} - s\right)!} \rho^{l-2s}. \quad (26)$$

This spectral representation fulfills the constraint on analytic functions (46) and enables analytical gradient computation of the geometric coordinates with respect to the magnetic coordinates [8]. Correct analytical representation of physical scalars at the axis is important

for stability calculations [40]. DESC can minimize the non-linear force error, or strong form, $\mathbf{F} = dW_{\text{pot}}/d\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ in real space, requiring computation and memory for second order derivatives, or the potential energy, i.e. the weak form, (17) or many other compositions of targets in geometric or magnetic coordinates. Quasi-Newton or least-squares optimizers implemented in DESC enable super-linear convergence in the spectral system [8]

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{sc}}, \mathbf{c}) \approx \mathbf{0}. \quad (27)$$

The boundary conditions \mathbf{c} , the spectral coefficients \mathbf{x}_{sc} and the residuals $\approx \mathbf{0}$ can be evaluated on one of many grids, for example, a quadrature grid which precisely integrates the chosen Fourier Zernike basis over the whole plasma volume.

The optimization in DESC is carried out over parameters in a tangent space \mathbf{y} with a particular solution $\mathbf{x}_{\text{p,sc}}$, ensuring that all linear constraints are satisfied during minimization:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_{\text{sc}} &= \mathbf{c} \\ \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{x}_{\text{p,sc}} + \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{y} &= \mathbf{c} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

DESC can utilize continuation methods to speed up convergence and computes spectrally dense solutions in the sense of equation (22). First, DESC solves an axisymmetric vacuum equilibrium which is then perturbed iteratively via two multipliers: $\eta_b \in [0, 1]$ for the toroidal boundary harmonics and $\eta_p \in [0, 1]$ for the pressure coefficients until both arrive at 1 and the final solution is obtained. The perturbations are Taylor expansions of the loss functional $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{y} + \Delta\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{c} + \Delta\mathbf{c})$ in some small parameter ϵ to find the first-order direction \mathbf{y}_1 [41] that satisfies the perturbed constraints $\mathbf{c} + \Delta\mathbf{c}$

$$\Delta\mathbf{y} = \epsilon\mathbf{y}_1 + \epsilon^2\mathbf{y}_2 + \dots \quad (29)$$

$$\Delta\mathbf{c} = \epsilon\mathbf{c}_1 \quad (30)$$

$$0 = \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{y}} \epsilon\mathbf{y}_1 + \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{c}} \epsilon\mathbf{c}_1 \quad (31)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_1 = - \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{y}} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{c}} \mathbf{c}_1 \right) \cdot \mathbf{y}_1 = - \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{y}} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{c}} \mathbf{c}_1 \right). \quad (32)$$

DESC uses concentric grids during minimization of the force residual by default, which are also used in this work.

The flexibility of DESC and the computation of analytic gradients in the Fourier Zernike basis facilitated recent extensions to include broader stellarator optimization, e.g. target functions for omnigenous magnetic fields optimized with constraints [42, 43].

2.3 Neural Networks applied to 3D ideal MHD equilibrium problems

One of the first publications about physics informed neural networks (PINNs) used MHD-based residuals in the domain of magnetically confined plasmas as loss functions to train NNs [20, 44, 45]. Already then, VAN MILLIGEN, TRIBALDOS and JIMÉNEZ [44] describe that solutions using MLPs need no finite-difference scheme, hinting at automatic differentiation. Their approach requires a transformation from Fourier representation to real space and provides one of the first PINNs to solve axisymmetric plasma equilibria. In a follow-up publication, they show the initial feasibility of representing three-dimensional plasma equilibria with NNs using L_2 -distance to data generated by VMEC [20]. These approaches were not pursued further until a decade later. The first application of NNs to equilibria of a real machine is presented by SENGUPTA et al. [46]: A vacuum dataset in the space of the stellarator W7-X is used to train a NN as a first step towards fast equilibrium reconstruction. A follow-up publication deprecated the NNs in favor of polynomials that showed similar performance to the NNs models [47].

Driven by the availability of modern algorithms and hardware, MERLO et al. [48] introduced a specialized operator NN model that reproduces flux surface geometries over most of the operational space of W7-X. This operator NN was trained on a dataset of flux surface geometries, their first-order gradients as calculated by VMEC and a surrogate force residual which assumes $F_h = 0$. Progress made by MERLO et al. [16] accelerated equilibrium reconstruction in the Bayesian framework *Minerva* [49, 50], which is used to interpret experimental data at W7-X. Remarkably, the inclusion of a physics-based residual during training improves the accuracy of the operator model.

JANG et al. [51] first introduced operator PINN for the direct map $NN : (R, Z, P, \epsilon, \kappa, \delta) \in \mathbb{R}^6 \mapsto \Psi(R, Z, P, \epsilon, \kappa, \delta) \in \mathbb{R}$ trained solely on physics targets over a space of axisymmetric tokamak equilibria. Both R and Z coordinates are inputs of the NN, P is a parameter for the pressure profile, ϵ is the inverse aspect ratio, the elongation is κ and δ is the triangularity. The NN's output is the total enclosed toroidal flux Ψ , which is sufficient to describe the direct map $(R, Z) \mapsto \Psi$ in axisymmetry.

The advances of [16] and [48], which used large models and large datasets, motivated this investigation of simple NNs that parametrize Fourier modes to minimize the ideal MHD equilibrium force residual. Before training larger operator models, we want to take a step back and find a lower bound on the NN complexity to parametrize solutions with low residual (see e.g. figures 6b and 6a). Furthermore, VAN MILLIGEN, JIMÉNEZ and

Figure 1: Illustration of the fully differentiable computational graph with NNs parameters ν_X and associated derivatives $\partial_{\nu_X} \|\mathbf{F}\|_2$. The inverse Fourier transform is marked with \mathcal{F}^{-1} . Computing the MHD force residual requires first and second order gradients of (R, λ, Z) with respect to ρ .

TRIBALDOS [20] showed that a single equilibrium problem can be solved by optimising parameters of a one-hidden-layer NN from which we extrapolate and employ NN with two-hidden layers to solve single equilibria. Figure 1 illustrates the computational graph of this work.

3 Physics informed Neural Networks

Physics informed machine learning leverages NNs to approximate solutions to partial differential equations [52]. In the PINN framework, a stationary PDE is formulated as

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{N}u(\mathbf{x}) = f(\mathbf{x}), & \mathbf{x} \in \Omega \\ \mathcal{B}u(\mathbf{x}) = g(\mathbf{x}), & \mathbf{x} \in \partial\Omega \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

on the (fully) connected domain $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}^d$ bounded by $\partial\Omega$. The partial differential operator of the PDE is \mathcal{N} and the PDE can be of hyperbolic, elliptic, parabolic or mixed type. \mathcal{B} denotes a Dirichlet, Neumann or Robin boundary condition operator on $\partial\Omega$. $f(\mathbf{x})$ is some homogeneous or inhomogeneous function and $g(\mathbf{x})$ are the boundary conditions. The PDE is solved on coordinate points in dimension d : $\mathbf{x} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d\}^\top \in \Omega \in \mathbb{R}^d$ which are the argument of some function $u(\mathbf{x}) = u_\nu(\mathbf{x})$ with parameters ν .

A quadratic residual function is then constructed as a target

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{\text{PINN}, \mathcal{B}} = & \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega} \|\mathcal{N}u_\nu(\mathbf{x}) - f(\mathbf{x})\| \\ & + \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x} \in \partial\Omega} \|\mathcal{B}u_\nu(\mathbf{x}) - g(\mathbf{x})\| \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

where $\mathbb{E}(x)$ denotes the expectation operator. Then, the optimization problem for the optimal parameters ν^*

becomes

$$\nu^* = \arg \min_{\nu} \mathcal{L}_{\text{PINN}, \mathcal{B}}(\nu). \quad (35)$$

Solving a PDE as an optimization problem introduces challenges from optimization into the minimization of $\mathcal{L}_{\text{PINN}, \mathcal{B}}$, for example, getting stuck at local minima. A common simplification to solve the optimization problem (35) is the exact imposition of boundary conditions by modifying the output $u_{\nu}(\mathbf{x})$. Constructing a monotonic function $\Phi(\mathbf{x})$ along the inward pointing normal vector on $\partial\Omega$ with approximate distance functions, such that $\Phi(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \forall \mathbf{x} \in \partial\Omega$ and $\Phi(\mathbf{x}) > 0 \forall \mathbf{x} \in \Omega$, decreases computational cost and can increase the final accuracy for many combinations of PDEs and PINNs [53]. In the case of homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions, the second part of the loss function (34) is removed by modifying

$$\bar{u}_{\nu}(\mathbf{x}) = g(\mathbf{x}) + \Phi(\mathbf{x})u_{\nu}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (36)$$

to exactly satisfy the boundary condition for $\mathbf{x} \in \partial\Omega$. In terms of equation (34) this step reduces the loss function to $\mathcal{L}_{\text{PINN}} = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega} \|\mathcal{N}u_{\nu}(\mathbf{x}) - f(\mathbf{x})\|$ and removes issues associated with weighting boundary loss against domain loss. The presented approach will only use this type of loss formulation.

The name *Physics-informed Neural Network* specifically refers to one or more NNs with parameters optimized to minimize some PDE residual. They do not require labelled data, such that the concept of PINN's may be viewed as an unsupervised learning strategy [54].

3.1 PINNs applied to the 3D ideal MHD equilibrium problem

The PINN approach solves the stellarator-symmetric ideal MHD equilibrium problem in the spectral representation (19-21) which also serves as the interface between VMEC and other codes. It replaces VMEC's finite-difference with automatic differentiation gradients and moves the parameters to the weights and biases of three NNs, one for each dependent coordinate $NN_{X, mn}(f(\rho); \boldsymbol{\nu}_X) : \mathbb{R} \cap (0, 1) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{M(2N+1)-N}$ with parameters $\boldsymbol{\nu}_X$ for $X \in \{R, \lambda, Z\}$ and two hidden layers. We briefly tested NNs with only one hidden layer but our results were not performant compared to two hidden layers. This serves as the map from the radial coordinate $\mathbf{x} := \rho \in (0, 1)$ to stellarator-symmetric Fourier modes $X_{mn} = \{R_{mn}^c, \lambda_{mn}^s, Z_{mn}^s\}$. The axis ($\rho = 0$) and boundary ($\rho = 1$) are not included during optimization. $NN_{R, mn}$ and $NN_{Z, mn}$ represent the Fourier modes with a distance function $\Phi(\rho) = (1 - \rho^2)$ akin to equation (36)

$$X_{mn}(\rho) = X_{bmn} + (1 - \rho^2)NN_{X, mn}(f(\rho); \boldsymbol{\nu}_X). \quad (37)$$

This ensures that the modes coincide with the prescribed boundary modes at $\rho = 1$, thereby reducing the dimensionality of the optimization space. The boundary modes for R and Z are specified up to some maximum poloidal M_b and toroidal N_b mode number. λ_{mn} profiles are free of this restriction. Interpolation of $m = 0$ modes between axis and boundary serves as initial guess enforced via the last layer's bias of $NN_{R, 0n}$ and $NN_{Z, 0n}$:

$$b_{L, X, 0n} = X_{a0n} - X_{0n}(\rho = 0) \quad X \in \{R, Z\} \quad (38)$$

Initializing the Fourier modes for R and Z this way intends to roughly reproduce VMEC's initialization by assuming mode-profiles of the form $X_{mn} = sX_{amn} + (1 - s)X_{bmn}$, ignoring some scaling factors used in VMEC. Modes with $m \geq 1$ require a fit at initialization because of the dependence on ρ^m in equations (40) and (42) and are set to 0. Subtracting the initial axis modes $NN_{X, 0n}(\rho = 0)$, this scheme can accommodate initial NN weights, which are sampled from a normal distribution, with magnitudes of order $\mathcal{O} \sim 10$ and higher without overlapping flux surfaces.

If an initial guess constructed with the mimicked VMEC interpolation is not nested or initial axis modes are not provided, a new initial guess for the axis X_{a0n} is computed using an invertible mapping to boundary conforming coordinates [55]. Given $\iota(\rho)$, $p(\rho)$ and X_{bmn} , the solver then optimizes the weights of each NN by minimizing

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{PINN}} = \sum_i (\|\mathbf{F}(\rho)\|_2)_i. \quad (39)$$

where $\mathbf{F}(\rho)$ is the ideal MHD force residual (14) which is summed over all grid points.

The residual (39) is optimized by two optimizers: The initial minimization is performed by a first-order optimizer (AdamW), and the second minimization uses optimizers that approximate the Hessian (BFGS) and is stopped when the parameters do not change anymore or upon reaching some $\langle \mathbf{F} \rangle_{\text{vol, norm}}$ (only used in figure 7 for the NN solutions).

Training of NN is often split into *batches* but here we do not split the geometric grid and train on separate batches, but optimize on all grid points at once in each iteration step.

Independent spectral resolutions in M and N for each dependent vector of modes R_{mn}^c , λ_{mn}^s and Z_{mn}^s are configurable in the solver, but not investigated in this study. A more detailed description of the NNs is provided in Appendix B.

Continuation methods that change the geometric or spectral resolutions as common practice in DESC (section 2.2) or VMEC (section 2.1) are not used.

$$R(\rho, \theta, \zeta) = \sum_{m=0, n=-N}^{M-1, N} \rho^m [R_{\text{bmn}} + (1 - \rho^2) NN_{R, mn}(f(\rho); \boldsymbol{\nu}_R)] \cos(\varphi_{F, mn}) \quad (40)$$

$$\lambda(\rho, \theta, \zeta) = \sum_{m=1, n=-N}^{M-1, N} \rho^m [NN_{\lambda, mn}(f(\rho); \boldsymbol{\nu}_\lambda)] \sin(\varphi_{F, mn}) \quad (41)$$

$$Z(\rho, \theta, \zeta) = \sum_{m=1, n=-N}^{M-1, N} \rho^m [Z_{\text{bmn}} + (1 - \rho^2) NN_{Z, mn}(f(\rho); \boldsymbol{\nu}_Z)] \sin(\varphi_{F, mn}) \quad (42)$$

4 Results

4.1 Methodology

This section compares the numerical results of **VMEC** and **DESC** with the NN-based results in terms of the force residual (43). The goal of this comparison is to highlight the ability of the NNs to be the parametrization to compute some minimum force error on equal spectral resolution for iota-prescribed, fixed-boundary equilibria. A more detailed runtime comparison between **DESC** and the NN-based results concludes this section.

The residual is normalized with the volume averaged magnitude of the magnetic pressure gradient (15) to ensure a fair comparison between equilibria

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{norm}} = \frac{|\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B} - \nabla p|}{\langle |\nabla B|^2 / (2\mu_0) \rangle_{\text{vol}}}. \quad (43)$$

All shown equilibria are prescribed with power profiles for $\iota(\rho)$ with coefficients a_l and $p(\rho)$ with coefficients a_m : $p(\rho) = \sum_m \rho^{2m} a_m$ and analogous for $\iota(\rho)$.

VMEC serves as a qualitative benchmark for magnetic flux surface topology. In the following, we compare the flux surface geometry of the NN-based solution to those of **VMEC** by visually overlaying both Poincaré plots at $\zeta = 0$ in figure 2 and 4 for ten flux surfaces including the last surface. Each Poincaré comparison also shows arcs of the straight field line poloidal angle $\theta^* = \theta + \lambda(\rho, \theta, \zeta)$ at eight equidistant locations.

The normalized force residual (equation (43)) offers a more reliable, quantitative metric, and its flux surface average $\langle \mathbf{F}_{\text{norm}} \rangle$ is plotted next to each Poincaré comparison for the three solvers. Computational runtime and accuracy in terms of the volume averaged $\langle \mathbf{F}_{\text{norm}} \rangle$ are compared only between **DESC** and NNs, because **DESC** and the NN-based approach need to be run on modern graphical accelerators to compute high resolution 3D equilibria in reasonable time and because both solvers compute solutions without **VMEC**'s force residual spike. Volume averaging \mathbf{F}_{norm} provides a scalar value to com-

pare different solutions of one equilibrium

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathbf{F} \rangle_{\text{vol, norm}} &= \langle \mathbf{F}_{\text{norm}} \rangle_{\text{vol}} \\ &= \frac{1}{V} \int \mathbf{F}_{\text{norm}} \sqrt{g} d\alpha. \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

The equilibrium solutions shown in this work are calculated using **VMEC**'s or **DESC**'s convention for the smallest poloidal and toroidal resolution of the computational grid given some spectral resolution. The NN-based approach uses 50 flux surfaces for figure 2 and 32 for figure 4 without refinement and without exploiting stellarator up-down symmetry, that is $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$ for the NN's computational grid. All collocation points are equidistant in (ρ, θ, ζ) and are not changed during optimization for the NNs. For all equilibria we use the minimal amount of grid points recommended to run **VMEC**, which is $2M + 6$ poloidal grid points and $2N + 4$ toroidal grid points for the NN solutions.

Exact parameters can be found in the supplemental material and a mathematical description of the MLP is provided in Appendix B. The computational grids in **DESC** use double the amount of grid points for each L_{ZP} , M_D and N .

The minimization of each **DESC** solution follows a two-step procedure using the least-squares optimizer: First, the solution is computed using the default continuation algorithm with default tolerances. A secondary solve (at $\eta_b = 1$ and $\eta_p = 1$) then reduces the optimizer tolerances to 0, approximating machine precision. Default geometric and spectral resolutions are used in **DESC**, and the axisymmetric tokamak is solved with fringe spectral indexing of the Zernike polynomial while W7-X is solved with ansi indexing.

Examples for fixed-boundary equilibria are, on the one hand, a tokamak taken from **HIRSHMAN** and **WHITSON** [7], and, on the other hand, a $M_b = N_b = 12$ W7-X equilibrium in standard configuration presented in **PANICI** et al. [40]. Both equilibria come with an initial guess for the magnetic axis. Many other fixed-boundary, finite- β equilibria can be compared, but we choose these two equilibrium cases because they have already been compared between **VMEC** and **DESC** [40].

The remainder of the results compare DESC and various sizes of the two-hidden-layer NNs, using the W7-X equilibrium with boundary harmonics truncated to $M_b = N_b = 10$. Figure 6a shows $\langle \mathbf{F} \rangle_{\text{vol, norm}}$ compared to DESC for the truncated W7-X equilibrium plotted over wall-time (both codes used a Nvidia A100 Graphical Processing Unit (GPU)). The same datapoints of figure 6a are used in figure 6b but with the global spectral resolution $M = N$ of the solvers on the x-axis. Finally, figure 7 shows the training of NNs with layer widths $n = \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16\}$ until the NNs $\langle \mathbf{F} \rangle_{\text{vol, norm}}$ matches the minimum $\langle \mathbf{F} \rangle_{\text{vol, norm}}$ computable with DESC for the boundary-truncated W7-X equilibrium. The NN minimization uses only 32 flux surfaces in this comparison. Results for a Heliotron-like equilibrium as used in HIRSHMAN and WHITSON [7] and DUDT and KOLEMEN [8] are provided in the supplementary material, because analysis of possibly bifurcated equilibrium states would take considerably more effort.

We provide these comparisons not to create a notion of a *best* solver, because this is essentially not possible respecting all differences of the three solvers, but to show that the NN-based approach is competitive in time and minimum computable residual to modern solvers.

All hyperparameters for optimizers and NN and result data for each solver and equilibrium are provided in the supplementary material (see Appendix A).

4.2 Equilibrium solutions

Figure 2 displays a Poincaré comparison between NNs and VMEC of an axisymmetric, D-shaped tokamak with $\beta \sim 3\%$, computed with $M = 11$ poloidal modes. VMEC's grid is refined up to 2048 flux surfaces and reaches a final, minimum internal tolerance of 2×10^{-16} . We use this number of flux surfaces in VMEC because iterative refinement of the radial grid is a common technique to use in VMEC minimizations and this comparison focuses on equal spectral resolution. Each of the three NNs for this equilibrium has two hidden layers with $n = 8$ nodes. The boundary geometry of the D-shaped tokamak is given by

$$\begin{aligned} R_b &= 3.51 - \cos(\theta) + 0.106 \cos(2\theta) \\ Z_b &= 1.47 \sin(\theta) + 0.16 \sin(2\theta) \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

with input pressure profile $p(\rho) = 1600(1 - \rho^2)^2$, rotational transform $\iota(\rho) = 1 - 0.67\rho^2$ and total toroidal flux set to $\psi_b = 1$ Wb [7]. The flux surfaces of VMEC are plotted in red and the flux surfaces of the NNs in dashed green. DUDT and KOLEMEN [8] found a similarly good agreement between the flux surfaces as computed by VMEC and DESC. All three solvers converge to a similar location for the magnetic axis and qualitatively equal θ^* . The NNs improves the flux surface averaged force

error compared to DESC at this spectral resolution (figure 3), and both codes approach the same value close to axis. The force residual of VMEC displays the largest discrepancies in the vicinity of the axis and close to the boundary compared to the NNs and DESC. The normalized residual of VMEC rises to $\sim 10^{-1}$ at $\rho < 0.15$ while DESC and the NN-based solution do not show this spike close to the axis (see Appendix C).

To compare the three solvers for a non-axisymmetric case, we choose a W7-X equilibrium, akin to the standard configuration, with $M_b = N_b = 12$ boundary harmonics. PANICI et al. [40] compares DESC and VMEC solutions for this equilibrium, and we employ the same input specification used in that work for this analysis. VMEC's radial grid for this equilibrium is refined up to 1024 flux surfaces. The same trend as in the D-shaped tokamak solutions is visible in figures 4 and 5. Flux surfaces, θ^* and axis position agree qualitatively for VMEC and NNs, and their difference becomes most visible for the force residual $\langle \mathbf{F}_{\text{norm}} \rangle$ close to axis. VMEC's force residual increases at $\rho < 0.15$ while DESC and NNs converge to solutions without this spike. The NN's $\langle \mathbf{F}_{\text{norm}} \rangle$ decreases towards the axis compared to DESC.

Of interest to users of MHD equilibrium solvers is not only their physical validity but also their speed to find accurate solutions. Figure 6a to 7 compare DESC solutions with NN solutions for multiple cases of the truncated W7-X equilibrium. To perform scans on memory-limited hardware, the boundary of the equilibrium used in figures 6a to 7 is pruned to only include modes up to $M_b = N_b = 10$. Figure 6a and figure 6b compare the same data plotted against time on plot 6a and against internal resolution parameter $M = N = \{10, 12, 14\}$ on plot 6b to the right. The datapoints each describe one instantiation of the solver run until the optimizer does not update the parameters anymore; i.e. the optimizer is fully converged. Individual DESC runs are marked with a crossed square and NN results with a rhombus. NN-based solutions are plotted with layer widths of $n = \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16\}$ for each of $M = N = \{10, 12, 14\}$. On the same hardware, DESC computes its solutions faster, but with a higher final force residual compared to some of the layer width of the two-hidden-layer NNs. The NNs are able to achieve solutions with lower $\langle \mathbf{F} \rangle_{\text{vol, norm}}$ but at increased computational cost, which can be easily reduced by, for example, using a grid with $\theta \in [0, \pi)$ that removes duplicated nodes under stellarator symmetry. With increasing spectral resolution, both solvers show an exponential decreasing $\langle \mathbf{F} \rangle_{\text{vol, norm}}$ in figure 6b.

To answer the question of how DESC and the NNs compare in terms of compute resources, the $M_b = N_b = 10$ W7-X case is solved using DESC with the two-stage approach described in section 4.1 until parameters stop changing.

Figure 2: Poincare sections for a D-shaped tokamak test-case with boundary defined by (45). Dashed green lines represent the NNs solution with $n = 8$ hidden nodes and full red lines represent the VMEC solution, revealing a qualitative agreement in flux surface geometry. Profiles of $\theta^* = \theta + \lambda(\rho, \theta, \zeta)$ are plotted at eight θ^* locations from axis to boundary.

Figure 4: Poincare section for a $M_b = N_b = 12$ equilibrium of the W7-X stellarator solved with NNs with $n = 18$ hidden nodes in dashed green and VMEC in red. Both solutions agree with each other qualitatively. $\theta^* = \theta + \lambda(\rho, \theta, \zeta)$ profiles are plotted at eight θ^* locations from axis to boundary.

Figure 3: Normalized flux surface averaged force error for the solutions of VMEC, NNs and the DESC for the D-shaped tokamak test-case plotted over ρ . The NN optimization continued for about 100 times longer than DESC and VMEC but achieves lowest minimum force error over the whole volume. VMEC's force error spikes at $\rho < 0.2$.

Figure 5: Normalized flux surface averaged force error for VMEC, NNs and DESC for the $M_b = N_b = 12$ W7-X test-case plotted over ρ . The NNs achieve lowest minimum force error over the whole volume and the force residual of VMEC spikes at $\rho < 0.15$.

Figure 6: Minimum force error for W7-X standard configuration with $M_b = N_b = 10$ boundary harmonics with global resolutions $M = N = \{10, 12, 14\}$ computable by DESC and NNs with layer-widths of $n = \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16\}$. The colorbar indicates the number of parameters and the y-axis the normalized volume averaged force error (44) plotted over (a) time in seconds and (b) Fourier resolution parameter $M = N$.

Figure 7: DESC trained until convergence for the W7-X case pruned to $M_b = N_b = 10$ boundary harmonics. NN with layer widths $n = \{2, 4, 8, 16\}$ trained until DESC's $\langle \mathbf{F} \rangle_{vol, norm}$ reached within relative tolerance of 0.5%. Both codes are executed on the same GPU.

The minimum $\langle \mathbf{F} \rangle_{vol, norm}$ computable by DESC is then set as a stopping criterion for the NN training process, which computes equilibria that are within 0.5% relative tolerance with respect to this stopping criterion. The results of this test are plotted in figure 7 over the compute time in seconds on the x-axis. NN-based solutions achieve the same force error requiring more computational time, but with equal order of magnitude, which increases with increasing node number of the hidden layers. Notably, the NN training procedure has an additional slight overhead to compute $\langle \mathbf{F} \rangle_{vol, norm}$ at each optimization step to check if the stopping condition is fulfilled.

5 Discussion

The NN parametrization can be optimized to represent equilibrium solutions with lower residual compared to VMEC and DESC for most node numbers of the two hidden layers for the two presented equilibrium cases and the Heliotron equilibrium in the supplemental material (see Appendix A). Both the Fourier Zernike basis of DESC and the NN parametrization satisfy the analytic constraint on functions that represent physical scalars on the unit disc (46), improving upon VMEC by removing the force error spike towards the axis (see figures 3, 5 and Appendix C).

Optimizing the NN until the minimum computable force error of DESC incurs comparable computational cost (figure 7). But with more resources, the NN-based approach computes lowest force residuals for the tested equilibria and solvers (figures 5, 3 and 6b). It is unexpected that the NN approach is comparable in terms of cost given the tendency of NNs to get stuck in local minima, the naive initial weights drawn from some normal distribution and the common optimizers used in this work. Remarkably, the presented NN approach does not use continuation methods as used in DESC and neither does it use spectrally condensed representations as used in VMEC. The presented differences in computational cost could stem from using NNs or could be attributable to implementation nuances; this question can be answered by comparing only floating point operations to reach a certain residual of each code.

Training procedures of PINNs usually fit the low frequencies of the solution first, also known as spectral bias [56], and the presented approach could benefit from

it in terms of equation (22). One possible reason for the lower minimum force error is the interplay of optimizer with the truncated representation used in VMEC and DESC. Representing solutions to ideal MHD with truncated spectral resolution regularizes the equilibrium problem [28], which is why the results of this work might be explained by the universal function approximation theorem for deep narrow NNs [57]. The distance between $\langle \mathbf{F} \rangle_{\text{vol, norm}}$ of DESC and the NNs decreases with increasing spectral resolution (see figure 6b), adding another support to this explanation. As this efficiency comparison only relies on one equilibrium of W7-X in standard-configuration, this effect should be studied for many different equilibria and NN models.

Section 4 compares VMEC, DESC and the NN-based approach on small spectral and geometric resolutions to show the viability of the NN-based parametrization. Increasing the grid resolution of DESC could result in lower force residuals and running VMEC multiple times, using the axis of the previous run as initial guess for the next run, could reduce VMEC’s force residual further. This work focuses on performance and solution quality given low resolutions and single solves; therefore, improvements to DESC’s geometric or spectral resolution and VMEC’s resolutions or workflows are not explored. The number of parameters in DESC is tightly coupled to the chosen spectral parameters L_{ZP} , M_D and N . In VMEC, the number of parameters changes depending on the number of flux surfaces, M and N . The NN-based approach is the only one of the three solvers for which the number of parameters can be set independently of the resolution of the spectral basis or the geometric grid size. Understanding the advantages and disadvantages of this independence can lead to even faster and more accurate solvers and more sophisticated pre-conditioning methods applicable to all ideal MHD solvers.

The presented work provides value for future operator learning studies and the reduced residual for higher node numbers in the two hidden layers n shows benefits of using small NNs to parametrize Fourier modes of ideal MHD equilibria.

5.1 Future Work

Halving the grid in the poloidal coordinate, i.e. $\theta \in [0, \pi)$, removes collocation points which encode equal information in stellarator symmetry and is expected to be an enhancement that likely will increase the efficiency of the presented approach further.

MHD solvers are extensively used as inner loop in stellarator optimization and the normalized force residual is a metric for ideal MHD equilibrium solutions. Equilibria resulting from the outer stellarator optimization loop are implicitly determined by the individual solutions of the inner loop. Many solvers that compute stabil-

ity, transport or turbulence metrics use the resulting equilibrium magnetic field of the outer loop, motivating a sensitivity analysis of those metrics with respect to the residual of the inner loop’s MHD equilibrium solution. Computing these metrics for a single equilibrium solved by multiple solvers can help to validate the NN-based approach and provide an initial guess for their sensitivity with respect to the force error and solver. Costs associated with solving the ideal MHD equilibrium are tiny compared to stability, transport or turbulence calculations and those dwarf compared to the cost of building large devices, but lowering the force residual of the inner loop could, however, improve Pareto fronts in multi-objective stellarator optimization.

Quantifying information overlap between NN parametrizations of different but related equilibria can unlock faster and more precise convergence or pre-conditioning schemes and is a prerequisite for transfer learning and helpful for the design of operator models. Analyzing the basis function encoded by the NNs in this work is a first step in that direction.

Integration of these novel NN-based equilibrium solutions into the framework of the DESC code provides a test bench in terms of many stellarator optimization metrics implemented in DESC. This integration would shed some light on the question whether the lower residuals presented in this work are attributable to using NNs and Fourier basis, or whether the Fourier-Zernike basis of DESC with small spectral resolution upper-bounds force residuals.

Training a model for some operator on solution data in a continuous space of equilibria induces some epistemic error. Replacing the VMEC dataset with a dataset created with the presented approach could reduce the epistemic error of the operator model introduced by MERLO et al. [16] to acceptable levels for rapid stability analysis or other applications, for which the current models lacks precision.

This work only varied the node number of two hidden layers (see figures 6a, 6b and 7), but extending the search to varying the number of hidden layers and nodes could yield lower residuals.

The NNs hidden layer node numbers are purposely kept minimal and NNs with more capacity, on average, reach lower residuals for larger computational cost (see figure 6b), hinting at potential to improve the approach both in resource requirements and time by leveraging NN optimization techniques. This includes, but is not limited to, a search over NNs structures commonly used in the domain of PINNs, novel collocation point sampling techniques to increase optimization efficiency, an investigation into novel self-adaptive loss functions used in other PINNs, and more.

Investigating the interplay between spectral bias [56] and spectral width (see equation (22)) could reveal if

the NN-based parametrization of ideal MHD equilibria rather benefits from it instead of being handicapped. Also, future work could explore whether the strong form of the ideal MHD residual (equation (14)) is sufficient to remove spectral enhancements during optimization. A comparison between the codes based on floating point operations is out of scope for this work, but would shed light on the exact efficiencies of the three codes. However, with ever decreasing computational costs per unit compute, the time of researchers might be better utilized to develop novel numerical methods. Another worthwhile investigation is whether the presented results can be achieved without any NNs, solely by optimizing the second order force operator (44) over the parameters of the VMEC-like Fourier basis directly, using finite-difference gradients in radial direction. However, this is only interesting for solving single equilibria and any operator model requires an additional interpolating model, e.g. the small MLP used in this work.

6 Conclusion

This work presents a novel approach to solve fixed-boundary, finite- β ideal MHD equilibria with nested flux surfaces and isotropic pressure using NNs. It is the first MHD solver capable of adjusting its parametrization independently of the geometric or spectral resolution, and the results show some benefit to using higher hidden-layer node numbers n . For all tested equilibria, this approach achieves the lowest force residual compared to other common ideal MHD equilibrium solvers for most tested node numbers of the two-hidden-layer NNs. Minimization of the residual parametrized by the NNs until the minimum computable residual of the solver DESC for a W7-X equilibrium requires slightly more resources, but can, with higher computational cost, arrive at solutions with lowest residual for the tested solvers. The deliberate choice of small NNs in this initial exploration establishes a lower bound for the complexity of NNs representing a single equilibrium state, which could serve future work aimed at creating NN models for MHD operators. The current optimization procedure is purposely kept minimal, but the literature surrounding PINNs offers many enhancements such as novel optimizers, new NN structures and sampling techniques. These enhancements are very likely to yield even lower residuals at lower cost. The presented proof-of-principle of optimizing simple NNs to minimize ideal MHD residuals of a single 3D equilibrium provides a solid basis to extend these models to represent continuous, parametrized spaces of equilibria. Possible applications include the optimization of devices for a whole continuum of configurations, acceleration of intra-shot analysis workflows that rely on the equilibrium magnetic topology

and sophisticated control algorithms.

Appendix

Appendix A Data availability

Equilibria, models, some implementation files used in the presented work are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15720852>. The supplementary material also includes files that encode the presented NN solutions in VMEC's output file format. We also added plots showing the parallel current profiles and other plots of VMEC, DESC and the NNs to this material.

Appendix B Neural Networks

We intentionally use simple NNs to provide a lower bound on NN complexity: The NNs are two-layer ($L = 2$) MLPs with $\sigma = \tanh = (e^{2x} - 1)/(e^{2x} + 1)$ activation function and input $f(\rho) = 2\rho^2 - 1 \in \mathbb{R} \cap (-1, 1)$. Each NN is denoted by $NN_{X,mn}$ for $X \in \{R, \lambda, Z\}$ and defined by a composition of affine transformations with non-linearity

$$\begin{aligned} NN_{X,mn}(f(\rho)) &= W_{2,X}(\sigma(z_1(f(\rho)))) + b_{2,X} \\ z_1(f(\rho)) &= W_{1,X}(\sigma(z_0(f(\rho)))) + b_{1,X} \\ z_0(f(\rho)) &= W_{0,X}f(\rho) + b_{0,X} \end{aligned}$$

with dimensions $W_{0,X} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$, $W_{1,X} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $W_{2,X} \in \mathbb{R}^{(M(2N+1)-N) \times n}$, respective parameters $\boldsymbol{\nu}_X$ and node number of the two hidden layers n . The summand of layers $l = \{0, 1\}$ has dimension $b_{l,X} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and the last bias is of dimension $b_{2,X} \in \mathbb{R}^{(M(2N+1)-N)}$. Parameters of the NN weights $W_{l,X}$ are initialized by random sampling from a normal distribution with standard deviation $\sigma = 0.01$ and mean $\mu = 0$. The bias $b_{l < L, X}$ are initially set to 0 and $b_{L, X}$ are set such that the initial guess for the magnetic axis is satisfied (see section 3.1).

Appendix C Analytic constraint

The constraint on functions representing physical scalars with poloidal Fourier modes a_m near the axis of the unit disk [58], namely that R_{mn}/ρ^m and Z_{mn}/ρ^m do not blow up towards the axis, is

$$a_m(\rho) = \rho^m \sum_i a_{m,i} \rho^i \text{ for } i \in \{0, 2, 4, \dots\}. \quad (46)$$

For the axisymmetric solution shown in figures 2 and 3, the profiles of R_{mn}/ρ^m are plotted in figure 8. All equilibria solved by NNs show no blow-up close to the axis for R_{mn}/ρ^m and Z_{mn}/ρ^m .

Figure 8: R_{mn}/ρ^m modes of NN solution for axisymmetric D-shaped equilibrium.

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